

Lutein content, fatty acid composition and enzymatic modification of lutein from marigold (*Tagetes patula* L.) flower petals

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Abstract : Marigold flower (*Tagetes patula* L.) is a very good source of carotenoid mainly lutein. The marigold flowers of three varieties (orange, yellow and red) are utilized to extract the lutein present in it by using various solvents like hexane, acetone, petroleum ether and methanol. Among these solvents methanol showed the highest extractability (52.51%). Among the various marigold, orange variety content the maximum amount of lutein of 154.96 mg per gram of extract. The fatty acid composition of the ester fraction was determined and saturated fatty acid content was maximum (about 75%) and unsaturated fatty acid was about 25%. The lutein ester was also reacted with capric acid (C₁₀) in presence of *M. miehei* immobilized lipase and about 17.5% C₁₀ fatty acid was incorporated to produce modified lutein for application in various functional foods.

Keywords : Lutein, fatty acid, marigold petals, *Tagetes patula* L.

Introduction

Tagetes sp. a genus of herbs, commonly known as marigold is the member of Compositae family, native of Mexico and other warmer parts of America and naturalized elsewhere in the tropics and sub tropics. Some species have been introduced into the Indian gardens. The flower heads are generally yellow, orange and red in colour and contain several pigments which appear to vary with the source of material. Several carotenoids have been identified in the flowers and processes have been patented for the separation of xanthophyll fraction from petals for use in chicken feeds to enhance the yellow colour of chicken skin and eggs. For optimal egg yolk colouration, most studies have been focused on the profile of carotenoids present in the egg yolk after feeding carotenoids enriched diet¹⁻⁶. Lutein (C₄₀H₅₆O₂) i.e. 3,3'-dihydroxy β-carotene is a yellow plant pigment in the carotenoids family, occurring in all green structure of plants and also in many flower petals. Marigold flowers are also grown commercially in many regions of the world for the extraction of xanthophyll pigment and lutein from the florets. Lutein is more effective than carotene in inhibiting

the auto oxidation of cellular lipids and protecting against oxidant induced cell damage. Lutein and Zeaxanthin are the only two carotenoids that accumulated at high levels of human retina, particularly the macular region^{7,8}. Epidemiological studies have been shown that serum levels of lutein concentration seems to be safe and a low risk for developing cardiovascular diseases, several types of cancers, cataracts etc.⁹. Marigold flower petals are used as a colouring and flavouring agent in food and medicinally for inflammatory disease^{10,11}.

In the present study the lutein content, their extraction by various solvents, the fatty acids present in the esters of different types of marigold flower petals and enzymatic modification of lutein of Indian varieties have been investigated with a view to produce good quality lutein for commercial application.

Results and discussion

Four solvents were used to extract lutein ester from marigold flower petals of different varieties available in Indian market. Table 1 shows the percent yield of the

extracts using *n*-hexane, petroleum ether, acetone and methanol. Among the solvents methanol showed the highest yield of 52.51%, 29.2% and 44.15% from orange (MGO), yellow (MGY) and red (MGR) colour marigold petal powders. This may be due to the strong polarity of the methanol in comparison with the other solvents. Among the different varieties of marigold orange variety (MGO) showed the highest productivity of lutein. Due to maximum productivity methanol extract was utilized for further study.

Table 1. Percent yield of crude extract from various types of marigold flower petal using different solvent

Types of marigold flower	Solvents			
	<i>n</i> -Hexane	Petroleum ether	Acetone	Methanol
MGO	7.98 ± 0.15	10.16 ± 0.26	13.49 ± 0.08	52.51 ± 0.53
MGY	4.8 ± 0.38	7.09 ± 0.15	7.32 ± 0.1	29.2 ± 1.8
MGR	6.82 ± 0.23	8.87 ± 0.07	12.12 ± 0.12	44.15 ± 0.74

Values are represent as a mean ±SD (n = 3).

Table 2 lists the lutein content of the methanol extracts of marigold flower petals. The orange variety showed the maximum lutein ester content of 154.96 mg per gram of extract. Lutein is present in the oil as ester of fatty acids. Table 3 shows the fatty acid composition of the lutein ester which was estimated by gas-liquid chromatographic technique. Among the saturated fatty acids, palmitic acid was maximum (37.1%) followed by myristic (21.4%), stearic (11.5%) and lauric (4.1%) acids. Among the unsaturated fatty acids linoleic acid was maximum of 15.2% followed by olein (5.6%) and linolenic (4.2%) acids.

Table 2. Total lutein content of different types of marigold flower petals (methanol extract)

Types of marigold flower	Total lutein content (mg/g of extract)
MGO	154.96 ± 1.08
MGY	12.67 ± 0.39
MGR	14.85 ± 1.09

Values are represent as a mean ±SD (n = 3).

Lutein ester (mainly diester) containing various essential or short chain fatty acids can be used as food colourants and also as nutraceutical components due to the presence of essential fatty acids as well as lutein. By using lipase catalysed reaction (with *Mucor miehei* lipase) capric acid has been incorporated in lutein ester at 17.51% level as a

medium chain fatty acid. Various short chain, medium chain and higher unsaturated fatty acids can be incorporated in lutein ester by lipase catalysed esterification and interesterification reaction to produce modified lutein for application in various functional foods. It is the first time report for modification of lutein by lipase catalysed reaction. Detailed investigation in this regard is going on.

Table 3. Fatty acid composition of the lutein ester (methanol extract)

Fatty acids	Percent (%) w/w
C _{10:0}	0.7 ± 0.27
C _{12:0}	4.1 ± 0.23
C _{14:0}	21.4 ± 2.5
C _{16:0}	37.1 ± 3.1
C _{18:0}	11.5 ± 0.5
C _{18:1}	5.6 ± 0.3
C _{18:2}	15.2 ± 4.2
C _{18:3}	4.2 ± 1.13

Values are represent as a mean ±SD (n = 3).

In India, a huge quantity of marigold flower is produced and mostly utilized as offering to God and decorative purpose and finally treated as a garbage or polluting nearby ponds and rivers. These flowers after their use can be collected for extraction of a valuable component as lutein extract. It can be utilized as natural colouring material in foods, as nutraceutical product, can be used in chicken feed to improve the colour and nutrition value of eggs or to produce structured lutein for medicinal purpose.

Materials and methods :

Plant material :

The flowers of *Tagetes patula* L. (Marigold) were procured from the local market and the petals were separated, sun dried, powdered and stored in a refrigerator for further studies.

Extraction of lutein from different types of marigold flower petals :

The coarse powder of the petals of marigold orange (MGO), marigold yellow (MGY) and marigold red (MGR) (about 50 g) was subjected to extraction with various solvents in a soxhlet apparatus independently with the increasing order of polarity from *n*-hexane, petroleum ether, acetone and methanol¹². The extraction was carried out

under dark condition. The extract was filtered and concentrated to a dry mass by distillation under vacuum and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for further study.

Determination of total lutein content of different types of marigold flower petals :

Total lutein content of the flower extracts of different types of *Tagetes patula* L. like MGO, MGY and MGR were determined using UV-Vis spectroscopic analysis¹³ at the absorption recorded at 445 nm. The experiment was performed in triplicate.

Isolation and identification of fatty acids from lutein esters of different types of marigold flower petals :

The concentrated extract of different types of marigold flower petals containing lutein esters was saponified in presence of 40% methanolic potassium hydroxide at $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h under dark condition. The unsaponifiable matter containing free lutein was extracted by three times using hexane. The water layer was acidified to liberate the free fatty acids and extracted three times with petroleum ether. The ether fractions were collected and the solvent was removed under vacuum. The fatty acids were converted to methyl ester by following standard procedure and fatty acid composition was analysed in a gas chromatograph instrument [Agilent 6890, Detector : FID, Column : polar DB Wax, 30 metre. (length), 0.25 mm i.d. and 0.25 mm (film thickness), packed with 100% polyethylene glycol; Conditions : Injector and detector block temperatures $-250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ respectively, Oven temperature programmed from $150\text{--}230\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ per minute; Nitrogen flow rate 1.5 ml/min as carrier gas].

Enzymatic modification of lutein :

The lutein ester was reacted with capric (C_{10}) fatty acid in a small round bottomed flask (1 : 3 molar ratio) in

presence of hexane at room temperature. Enzyme used was immobilized *Mucor miehei* (NOVOZYMES, South Asia Private Limited, Bangalore, India) lipase at 10% (w/w) level. The reaction was continued for 3 h. After the reaction the excess fatty acid was neutralized, the lutein ester was separated and the fatty acid composition was determined as mentioned above.

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References

1. T. Phillip, C. W. Weber and J. W. Berry, *J. Food Sci.*, 1976, **41**, 23.
2. J. K. Tyczkowski and P. B. Hamilton, *Pol. Sci.*, 1986a, **65**, 1526.
3. J. K. Tyczkowski and P. B. Hamilton, *Pol. Sci.*, 1986b, **65**, 1141.
4. J. L. Schaeffer J. K. Tyczkowski and C. R. Parkhurst, *Pol. Sci.*, 1988b, **67**, 608.
5. P. B. Hamilton, F. J. Tirado and F. Garcia-Hernandez, *Pol. Sci.*, 1990, **69**, 462.
6. S. M. Lai, J. I. Gray, C. J. Flegal and T. Cooper, *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, 1996, **72**, 166.
7. D. D. Kuzmicky, G. O. Kohler, A. L. Livingston, R. E. Knowles and J. W. Nelson, *Pol. Sci.*, 1969, **48**, 326.
8. R. A. Bone, J. T. Landrum, G. W. Hime and A. Cains, *Invest. Ophthalmol. Vis. Sci.*, 1993, **34**, 2033.
9. R. A. Bone, J. T. Landrum and S. L. Taris, *Vis. Res.*, 1985, **25**, 1531.
10. R. A. Bye (Jr.), *Econ. Bot.*, 1986, **40**, 103.
11. M. T. Khan, M. Potter and I. Birch, *Phytother. Res.* 1996, **10**, 211.
12. C. K. Kokate, in "Practical Pharmacognosy", 3rd ed., Vallabh Prakashan, New Delhi, 1994, p. 107.
13. F. Delgado-Vargues, in "Natural Colourants for Food and Nutraceutical Uses", CRC Press, USA, 2003, p. 142.